

Fig. 1. Structure of mixed ligand complexes ; R = H, CH₃, or C₂H₅.

The electronic absorption spectra of the mixed ligand Ni²⁺ complexes in methanol gave two bands in the region 610-620 and 535-550 nm which can be assigned to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ³B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ³B_{8g}, respectively. The Cu²⁺ complex (solution) gave one band in the region 635-645 nm which may be assigned to the transition ³B_{1g} → ³E_g. Solution spectra of the Pd²⁺ complexes exhibited three bands in the ranges 440-450, 375-380 and 315-320 nm assigned to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g}; ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u}, respectively. The Pt²⁺ complexes also gave three bands in the region 310-320, 350-355 and 420-430 nm assignable to the transitions ¹A₁ → ¹B₁, ¹A₁ → ¹A₂ and ¹A₁ → ³A₂, respectively. These data indicate a square-planar structure²⁻⁵ for the Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pd²⁺ and Pt²⁺ complexes.

In the ir spectra of complexes [MLL'] and [MLL'A], no bands have been observed in the region 3 300-3 100 or 3 600-3 400 cm⁻¹ indicating that hydrogen of the NH group of pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and OH group of acetylacetonate get dissociated on complexation. Spectra of the [MLL'] complexes show bands at 1 630 cm⁻¹ and 1 570 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to aldehydic C=O and C=O of the acetylacetonate, respectively. In the ir spectra of the [MLL'A] complexes (in which R=H), the band at 1 630 cm⁻¹ disappeared and a new band around 1 600 cm⁻¹ C=N of the imine linkage appeared. The band at 1 570 cm⁻¹ C=O of acetylacetonate remains unchanged indicating that it does not undergo condensation. The appearance of the band in the region 3 300-3 100 cm⁻¹ shows the presence of free N-H which was absent in the mixed ligand complexes derived from alkylamines. The ir spectra of the [MLE. H₂O] type complexes show a band around 3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH) which confirms the presence of water molecule, and a band at 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The appearance of two new bands in the region 500-480 and 5 0-560 cm⁻¹ in the above type of complexes suggest the presence of M-O and M-N bondings⁶ in them.

On the basis of the above investigations, the [MLL'], [MLL'A] and [MLE. H₂O] type complexes may be represented by the structures as shown in Fig. 1

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Stability Constants of Complexes of some Bivalent Metal Ions with *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline and *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline

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FROM the literature survey on the stability constants it is seen that no work on solution stability constants of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline and *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline has been reported so far. The present investigation is aimed at determining the stability constants of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Co²⁺, Cd²⁺, and Mg²⁺ with the above mentioned ligands.

Experimental

The reagents *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline and *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline, were synthesised by condensing ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with 2,6-dimethylaniline and 2,4-dimethylaniline, respectively in equimolar ratios. The products were repeatedly crystallised to get analytically pure compounds. The purity of the compounds was tested by tlc and elemental analysis; m.p. 135 and 99°, respectively.

Calvin-Bjerrum¹ titration technique was used to determine the dissociation constants of the reagents and the formation constants of their metal chelates at 30 ± 0.1° in 75 : 25 (v/v) dioxan-water medium at 0.1 M ionic strength.

A Elico Li-15 pH meter (division, 0.1 unit; temperature compensator range 0-100°) was employed throughout the investigation for pH determinations. The glass electrode supplied was used in combination with a dip type calomel electrode. Standardisation of the pH meter was resorted to by means of buffers 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4.019 at 30°) and 0.01 M borax (pH 9.18 at 30°). The metal ion solutions prepared from A. R. grade salts, were standardised by EDTA titrations². During the titrations oxygen-free nitrogen presaturated with solvent mixture was bubbled through the solutions. The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.075 M): (i) 5 ml 0.16 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.64 M NaClO₄ + 30 ml dioxan, (ii) 5 ml 0.16 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.64 M NaClO₄ + requisite amount of the reagent to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan, and (iii) 5 ml 0.64 M NaClO₄ + 5 ml metal perchlorate (0.008 M in 0.16 M HClO₄) + requisite amount of the reagent to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in final solution + 30 ml of dioxan. The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Results and Discussions

Formation functions, \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} , pL were calculated using the standard expressions from the titration curves, the pK_1^H and pK_2^H values of the ligands at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5, respectively were calculated (Figs. 1a and b). The values were further corroborated

from the plots of $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B and $\log (2-\bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A-1)$ vs B. The formation curves of metal-ligand systems were obtained by plotting \bar{n} vs pL (Figs. 2 and 3). From these curves the values of $\log K_1$ and K_2 were determined. The values obtained by half-integral method were further corroborated from the plots of $\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})$ vs pL and $\log (2-\bar{n})/(\bar{n}-1)$ vs pL . For those metal systems where difference between $\log K_1$ and

Fig. 1. Formation curves of (a) *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline and (b) *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline.

Fig 3. Metal-ligand systems of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline.

$\log K_2$ was less than 1.78 log units, the values were better determined by least-square method.

The pK_{OH}^H values of the ligands were examined in the light of mesomeric and inductive effects of the substituents. The pK_{OH}^H value of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline (b) is 9.83 and that of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline (a) is 10.30. In the compound (b), the two methyl groups are flanking the azomethine nitrogen and hence bring in the steric repulsion, interfering with the coplanarity of the anilino ring with the six-membered chelate ring formed by the intra-molecular hydrogen bonding. It may thus result in the weakening of the hydrogen bond due to lesser electron donation from the methyl groups, as a result the pK_{OH}^H value of the compound (b) is less than that of compound (a), although both the compounds have two methyl groups in the anilino ring. The order of the stability constants for the ligand *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-

2,6-dimethylaniline is $Cu^{II} > Co^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Cd^{II} > Mg^{II}$, and that for ligand *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline is $Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Co^{II} \approx Ni^{II} > Cd^{II} > Mg^{II}$.

In the present study, graphs of stability constants of the complexes of the bivalent metal ions of the first transition series of both the ligands were plotted against atomic number of the elements (Fig 4). It was observed that there was a monotonic rise to a maximum of Cu followed by a lower value of Zn. A similar relation was observed by Irving and Williams⁸. The plots also confirmed the observation that the stability seems to decrease with the increase in basicity of the metal, i.e. weakly basic metal like Cu forms stronger chelates and strongly basic metal like Mg forms weaker chelates⁴. The second ionisation potential rises along the transition series to a maximum of Cu and falls again at Zn. A correlation between second ionisation potential and complex stability was pointed out by other workers⁵⁻⁷. A similar relation was also observed in both the ligands under study (Fig. 5). Plots of $\log K$ of the same reagents

Fig. 4.
a (x)
b (O)

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 M$

<i>N</i> -(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline			<i>N</i> -(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline		
Cation	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	Cation	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
H ⁺	9.83	2.10	H ⁺	10.30	3.325
Cu ^{II}	9.00	—	Cu ^{II}	9.48	8.26
Co ^{II}	5.93	—	Zn ^{II}	6.40	—
Zn ^{II}	5.90	—	Co ^{II}	6.20	—
Ni ^{II}	5.73	—	Ni ^{II}	6.20	—
Cd ^{II}	4.77	—	Cd ^{II}	5.25	—
Mg ^{II}	4.37	—	Mg ^{II}	4.75	—

Fig. 5.
a (x)
b (O)

against reciprocal of ionic radii of transition metal ions (Fig. 6) show that the ligands form weak complexes with Mg and stable complexes with Cu than with other bivalent transition metal ions.

Fig. 6.
a (x)
b (○)

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Studies of Formation Constants of Cinnamohydroxamic Acid Complexes with Lanthanum(III), Neodymium(III) and Samarium(III)

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THE flexibility of the coordination number of the rare earth ions¹ makes it interesting to study the nature of the rare earth-hydroxamate bond in the complexes with different types of simple and

substituted hydroxamic acids^{2,4}. The determination of stability constant values of some of the lanthanide-hydroxamate complexes, particularly those with NBPFA, was made previously². In the present communication, the formation constant values of three lanthanide ions La^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} with cinnamohydroxamic acid (CHA) in dioxane-water medium (3 : 1, v/v) are reported.

Experimental

The ligand cinnamohydroxamic acid (CHA) was prepared by the method described earlier³. The reagent was repeatedly recrystallised before use. The purity of the reagent was verified by m.p. (110-111°) determination and matching of ir spectra.

The perchlorates of the lanthanides used were prepared by digesting the corresponding oxides (Johnson Matthey, 99.9% pure) with perchloric acid and removing the excess acid by repeated evaporation. Finally, the perchlorates were dissolved in water and made up to definite volumes. Lanthanide ions were determined by oxalate precipitation and subsequent ignition to respective oxides⁴. Free perchloric acid present in the metal perchlorate solution were determined by running a known volume of the solution through a column of Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺-form) and titrating the liberated acid with a standard sodium hydroxide solution⁵ and subtracting the quantity of acid liberated M(III) ions.

Purified dioxane⁶ and double-distilled (CO₂-free) water were used for making solutions. All other chemicals were of A R. grade.

Procedure: Experimental procedure consisted of titration of 40 ml dioxane-water (3 : 1, v/v) solutions containing $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion, $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ CHA and having a constant ionic strength (0.1 M) maintained by adding requisite amounts of sodium perchlorate with a standard solution of NaOH in an inert (nitrogen) atmosphere at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The pH measurements were made with a Cambridge pH meter having a glass electrode (Universal type) and a calomel electrode connected to the cell by salt bridge. The acid dissociation constant of CHA was determined by a similar titration of the ligand in the absence of metal ion pH meter was calibrated using aqueous buffer solutions and the readings were converted to the stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration incorporating correction for the use of mixed solvents⁷. The absence of polynuclear and hydroxo-complexes in the complexation equilibrium was checked by using two different concentrations of metal ions.

Results and Discussion

Successive formation constants K_1 , K_2 and K_3 were evaluated by analysing the formation function,

$$\sum_{n=0}^N (\bar{n}-n) [L^-]^n \beta_n \quad (1)$$